

SYNTHESIS OF COMPOUNDS ALLIED TO CHLOROMYCETIN. PART II

BY A. B. SEN AND D. D. MUKERJI

The *p*-amino and *p*-methoxy analogues of chloromycetin have been synthesised for evaluation of their therapeutic activity.

The antibacterial properties of chloromycetin are more connected with the three-configuration of the molecule and the presence of a *p*-substituent in the phenyl nucleus than with the nature of the substituent (Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 255). In view of this fact the *p*-amino and the *p*-methoxy analogues of chlororamphenicol have been synthesised.

Starting with acetanilide the *p*-amino analogue has been prepared following the method of Long and Troutman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2649) through the following stages:

Condensation of *p*-acetamido- α -acetamidoacetophenone (E) with formaldehyde

proceeded satisfactorily. The reduction of the propiophenone (F) derivative, thus obtained, was accomplished with aluminium isopropoxide. The principal product so obtained is the desired threo racemate.

The *p*-methoxy analogue has also been synthesised independently by following the same method. The details are not included in this paper as Buu Hoi *et al.* have already published results of their investigation (*loc. cit.*). In this case the only difference was in the preparation of the phenacyl bromide (B), which was obtained by us by dissolving anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene, to which was added slowly anisole and bromoacetyl bromide, keeping the temperature at 0°. This modification was introduced as it had been observed by Barnes and Gordon (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 5308) that often demethylation was effected in the Friedel-Crafts reaction when carbon disulphide was used as a solvent. We further observed that the yield of the *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide improved from 30-35% to 65% when nitrobenzene was used as a solvent.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Preparation of ω -Bromo-*p*-acetamidoacetophenone.*—The side-chain substituted bromoketone was prepared in good yield (70%) by slightly modifying the method of Kunckel (*Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 2641, 2644).

To a well stirred mixture of 15 g. of acetanilide (0.1 mole), 105 c.c. of dry carbon disulphide and 50 g. of bromoacetyl bromide, was added pulverised aluminium chloride (52.5 g, 0.4 mole). A large amount of heat was evolved and the reaction became vigorous. To moderate the reaction it was cooled with water. After keeping for 6 hours at the room temperature, it was refluxed on a water-bath for about an hour. The carbon disulphide was then distilled off and the thick liquid was poured in crushed ice containing a little concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solid so obtained was filtered and recrystallised from *n*-amyl alcohol, m.p. 190°, yield 22 g.

*Hexamethylenetetramine Salt of *p*-Acetamido- ω -bromoacetophenone.*—To a well stirred mixture of powdered hexamethylenetetramine (0.06 M, 8.8 g.) in 52 c.c. of dry chloroform was added in one portion with stirring, *p*-acetamido- ω -bromoacetophenone (0.05 M, 13 g.) in 52 c.c. of dry chloroform. The temperature was raised to 50°-52° and maintained for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled to 30° and filtered. The filtered cake was stirred with 24 c.c. of ethanol and filtered, m.p. 186° (cf. *Chem. Abst.*, 1915, 1610).

p-Amino- α -aminoacetophenone Hydrochloride.—The hexamethylenetetramine salt obtained from 13 g. of *p*-acetamido- ω -bromoacetophenone was added to a solution (25°) of 42 c.c. of ethanol (95%) and 18 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid in a 250 c.c. three-necked flask fitted with a stirrer and a thermometer. A red solution was formed at first, after which crystals of the hydrochloride began to separate out. The stirring was continued at room temperature for 12 hours. After which it was cooled to 5° and filtered. The crystalline product consisting of the amine hydrochloride and ammonium chloride was then stirred for 15 minutes with 25 c.c. of water (25°), and filtered. The product was dried *in vacuo* over calcium chloride, m.p. 204°-206°, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 52.0; H, 5.3; N, 14.6. Calc. for C₁₁H₁₁ON₂Cl: C, 51.4; H, 5.8; N, 15.0 per cent.)

p-Acetamino- α -acetaminoacetophenone.—*p*-Amino- α -aminoacetophenone hydrochloride (10 g.) was mixed with 40 c.c. of water and 90 g. of chipped ice in a 250 c.c. three-necked flask. Acetic anhydride (13 g.) was added to the mixture and stirred for 5 minutes, while a solution of 17.5 g. of sodium acetate (crystalline) in 65 c.c. of water was added rapidly. The solution turned red and crystals gradually separated out.

The mixture was then further stirred until the temperature was raised to 20°. It was then made acidic with concentrated hydrochloric acid and filtered. The pale yellow product was washed several times with water and dried, m.p. 218-20°, yield 5.5 g. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 5.8; N, 11.4. Calc for $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_2$: C, 61.5; H, 6.0; N, 11.06 per cent).

p-Acetamino- α -acetamino- β -hydroxypropiofenone.—To *p*-acetamino- α -acetaminoacetophenone (5 g.) were added 12 c.c. of 95% ethanol and 4 c.c. of 36-38% aqueous formaldehyde in a 250 c.c. three-necked flask, fitted with a stirrer and a thermometer. Sodium bicarbonate (0.2 g.) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2 hours at 35°. A clear solution was formed after stirring for a short while. Stirring was continued for two hours and crushed ice was added to it till a turbidity appeared. It was then left in a refrigerator overnight for settling down the crystals. The crystalline product was then filtered and dried, m.p. 58-60°, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 5.0; N, 10.2; Calc for $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2$: C, 59.0; H, 5.3; N, 10.6 per cent).

dl-threo-1-*p*-Acetamidophenyl-2-acetamido-1:3-*propanediol*.—*p*-Acetamido- α -acetamido- β -hydroxypropiofenone (3.5 g.) was added to a hot solution of freshly distilled aluminium isopropoxide (6 g.) in 50 c.c. of dry isopropyl alcohol in a 100 c.c. flask equipped with a stirrer and a Hahn condenser. After a few minutes' stirring an opaque, red-brown solution was formed. Stirring and removal of acetone was continued for 4 hours.

The thick red-brown residue was allowed to cool just below reflux temperature and 5 c.c. of water were then added. The mixture was then refluxed for 15 minutes and filtered. The residue was twice refluxed with additional 25 c.c. of isopropyl alcohol. The combined extracts were concentrated *in vacuo* and the residue was refluxed with 20 c.c. of ethyl acetate till the oily material dissolved. It was cooled to 20° and filtered. The crystalline product so obtained was recrystallised from water, m.p. 183-85°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 57.0; H, 6.3; N, 10.2. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2$: C, 57.9; H, 6.7; N, 10.5 per cent).

dl-threo-1-*p*-Aminophenyl-2-amino-1:3-*propanediol*.—A mixture of the diacetyl derivative (0.3 g.) and 5 c.c. of 5% hydrochloric acid was heated on a steam-bath with occasional swirling. The solid dissolved within a few minutes and the resulting solution was heated for an hour at 95°. The pale yellow solution was cooled to 20° and made strongly basic with 20% aqueous sodium hydroxide. It was then extracted several times with small portions of ethyl acetate. The combined extracts then dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate and filtered. On concentrating the ethyl acetate extract in a dish, the desired substance was obtained, m.p. 93-95°, yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 59.0; H, 7.3; N, 14.8. Calc for $C_8H_{14}O_2N_2$: C, 59.34; H, 7.7; N, 15.38 per cent).